

DATA COLLECTION FORM

Side A

Code: Age: Sex:

MARITAL STATUS	1.Single	2.Married	3. Divorced /widowed			
EMPLOYMENT STATUS	1.Active	2.Retired		3. Unemployed	4. Housewife	
EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	1. Illiterate	2. Primary school	3. Secondary school	4. technical	5. Higher	
CAUSE OF KIDNEY DISEASE	1. T2M	Hypertension	3.Nephritis	5.Glomerulonephitis		6. Unknown
COMORBIDITIES	1.T2M	2.Cardiac disease/ hypertension	3.Cancer	4. Peripheral vascular disease	5. Cerebrovascular disease	6. Hepatitis C
DURATION OF DIALYSIS (IN YEARS):	Sleep disorders: (yes) (no)		Number of medicines: 1: 1 to 3 () 2: 4 to 6 () 3: > 6			

WEIGHT:	SIZE:	BMI:
Albumin:	Haemoglobin:	Phosphorus:
Creatinine:	Ferritin:	parathyroid hormone:
Urea:	Calcium:	blood glucose: CRP: